

Research article

LEVEL OF COORDINATION BETWEEN THE HUMANITARIAN AND GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS IN GAZA STRIP AND ITS IMPACT ON THE HUMANITARIAN INTERVENTIONS TO THE INTERNALLY DISPLACED PEOPLE (IDPS) FOLLOWING MAY ESCALATION 2021

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Abstract: In Gaza Strip, where emergencies always occur leading to devastating humanitarian consequences, both the governmental and the humanitarian non-governmental organizations need to work together to serve the affected communities. This study aimed at identifying the level of coordination that exists between the humanitarian organizations and its impact on the humanitarian interventions provided in response to the IDPs of May escalation 2021. To achieve its objectives, the study used the descriptive analytical approach where interviews were conducted with relevant stakeholders. The study mainly found that the coordination is an essential component of the humanitarian and governmental organizations' work that positively impact the efficiency of their interventions and that both humanitarian and governmental organizations coordinate and partner with each other and with relevant stakeholders including governmental and non-governmental organizations and it also found that the level of coordination in response to May escalation of hostilities reached 80 per cent however more improvements are required for effective interventions and response. The study recommended humanitarian organizations to accelerate their response to the emergency status and make use of their resources available as quickly as possible to avoid causing negative impact and that the IDPs working group under the Inter-Cluster Coordination Group to be activated to improve the response to IDPs and to improve the coordination and collaboration between the governmental and humanitarian organizations to the greatest extent possible for further effective response.

Keywords: Coordination, Gaza Strip, Humanitarian Interventions, IDPs, May Escalation

1. Introduction

Humanitarian interventions usually involve a significant number of national and international entities working in the same geographic areas and pursuing the same broad objectives. However, coordination and collaboration among them are frequently limited at best. In any given emergency response, failure to collaborate might result in coverage gaps, duplications, and inefficiencies (Saavedra and Knox-Clarke, 2015). During conflicts, where infrastructure, people, services and humanitarian aid providers themselves may be targets, the factors and choices influencing aid interventions are more complex than in non-conflict settings (Sanderson, 2019). And as humanitarian requirements escalate during such times, governments and humanitarian organizations need to anticipate, prepare for and respond to crises more successfully (OCHA, 2012). For a successful disaster management, effective coordination and collaboration among stakeholders is required at international, regional, national and organizational level (Migdad, 2012).

Coordination is considered a key operational principle for any effective response to disasters. It helps avoid duplication in the efforts targeting the affected population and is crucial to strengthen the interaction between humanitarian institutions and national and local governments to quickly respond and prevent any losses or damages that may result from disasters. For the UN system, governments, and non-governmental organizations, coordination is a vital component of disaster prevention, mitigation, readiness, and response (Pathirage, et al., 2008). According to organizations engaged in emergencies, three levels of coordination have been identified: communication, where information and knowledge is shared between organizations; alignment, where organizations 'may adjust their activities to create a more effective response on the basis of the activities of other organizations', for example ensuring they work in different neighborhoods; and collaboration, where organizations may have common goals and share activities (Sanderson, 2019).

Over the years, Gaza has suffered from multiple escalations killing and injuring thousands of people, destroying and damaging thousands of buildings and housing units and creating extreme unending vulnerabilities. And as the government capacities to deal with the recurrent Israeli hostilities over Gaza were always not enough, the humanitarian community and its organizations had to intervene to provide the assistance and relief to the affected population, reduce their vulnerabilities and increase their resilience. Such interventions were conducted either directly with the related ministries or in a coordinated manner that is led by the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA).

2. Problem Statement

The level of coordination between the humanitarian community and governmental organizations was perceived differently with a number of variables affecting it, here comes the need to assess that level of coordination in the recent crisis that hit Gaza Strip which is the escalation of hostilities in May 2021.

This was witnessed through the delay in taking the decision of opening UNRWA's Designated Emergency Shelters (DES) by UNRWA and the government in Gaza and providing the response to the displaced civilian people during the escalation. While the humanitarian interventions from a number of humanitarian agencies' side were provided since the beginning of the escalation, there were few obstacles concerning the service delivery.

From those points, it was important to measure if the level of coordination during the escalation was enough and effectively responding to the needs of IDPs from both the governmental and non-governmental organizations' points of view.

What is the level of coordination between the humanitarian and governmental organizations and its impact on the humanitarian interventions to the Internally Displaced People (IDPs) following May escalation 2021?

From this main question, the following sub-questions are derived:

- How responsive the humanitarian international organizations were to the urgent coordination efforts?
- What are the tools of coordination between the humanitarian and governmental organizations?
- How the coordination processes between the humanitarian organizations are managed?

3. Study Goals

This study aimed at assessing the level of coordination between the humanitarian organization and the governmental bodies in Gaza and its impact on the humanitarian interventions to the IDPs of May escalation through the below sub-goals:

- Identify the nature, level and tools of coordination among the governmental organizations.
- Identify the nature, level and tools of coordination among the humanitarian organizations.
- Measure the impact of coordination on humanitarian interventions.
- Determine the impact of the coordination level on the response targeting IDPs of May 2021 escalation on Gaza.

4. Study Importance

By identifying the level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations in Gaza specially in response to May escalation, this study will:

1. Provide a clear picture on whether the level of coordination is enough and is supporting the affected people and meeting their needs.
2. Shed light on the gaps in the response provided following May escalation.
3. Suggest ways to improve the coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations to respond effectively.
4. Develop the researcher's capacities in the field of coordination and humanitarian interventions.

5. Study methodology

The study used the case study and the descriptive analytical approaches. To apply the methodology, interviews which questions were derived from humanitarian coordination tools were used

Study Population:

Humanitarian and governmental organizations working in Gaza Strip and responded to May escalation in 2021.

Study Sample:

Representatives of one governmental organization (Ministry of Social Development) and two humanitarian organizations – one local NGO and one INGO – OXFAM and AISHA Association for Women and Child Protection

Study variables

Study Terminologies

Coordination:

Coordination is the orderly utilization of arrangement instruments to convey compassionate help with a durable and powerful way. Such instruments incorporate vital arranging; gathering information and overseeing data, preparing assets and guaranteeing responsibility, organizing a utilitarian division of work, arranging and keeping up a serviceable structure with have political experts and giving initiative (Minear et al. 1992).

Humanitarian organizations:

Entities with a mission to prevent and/or alleviate human suffering in armed conflicts. They are usually involved in: searching for, collecting and transporting the wounded and sick, missing and dead; providing medical treatment to the wounded and sick; assisting prisoners of war; and assisting the civilian population through the provision of humanitarian relief. They are also sometimes referred to in IHL as impartial humanitarian bodies (ICRC).

Local government institutions: Local government institutions may comprise of municipal governments, boards of education, district health boards and a variety of other special purpose institutions. These institutions provide services needed by their residents, such as land use planning, roads, utilities, public transit, economic development promotion, education, health services, and infotainment (IGI Global).

May escalation:

The 11-days of intense fighting, 10-21 May 2021, between Israeli forces and Palestinian armed groups in the Gaza Strip, was the gravest since 2014. In Gaza, scores of civilians were killed and injured. Tens of thousands were displaced. Homes and vital infrastructure were destroyed or damaged and the supply of basic services was severely disrupted. The outbreak

of hostilities followed weeks of rising tension in East Jerusalem around access restrictions of Palestinians to holy sites during the month of Ramadan and the threat of forced eviction of Palestinian families by the Israeli authorities in Sheikh Jarrah (OCHA, 2021).

Humanitarian interventions:

Is a set of measures the organization working in the emergencies' field apply after the emergency occurs where those organizations work in all phases of emergencies in order to mitigate their impacts. It includes financial interventions and cash assistance, psychological interventions and others (Abu Dayya, 2019).

IDPs:

Internally displaced persons (IDPs), according to the *United Nations Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement*, are “persons or groups of persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular as a result of or in order to avoid the effects of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights or natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized state border” (UNHCR).

Previous studies

The Role of Coordination between Municipal Councils and Local Government's Entities on Level of the Services Provided in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: an Exploratory Study - (El Elwan, 2020)

The study aimed at identifying the role of coordination between municipal councils and other local government's entities on the level of provided services. The study used both the descriptive analytical method. The results of this study showed that the level of coordination between municipal councils and other local governmental service providers is moderate and that the current level of coordination between municipal councils and other local service providers of governmental entities affects the level and quality of provided services. The study recommended the need to increase the level of coordination between municipal councils and the government and different councils and that the regulations and legislation that support coordination to be set between municipal councils and other local service providers of governmental entities.

Assessing the Management of International Humanitarian Interventions in Crises in the Gaza Strip - (Abu Dayya, 2019)

The study aimed at evaluating the management of the international humanitarian interventions in the Gaza Strip during crises and identifying the most effective types of humanitarian interventions. The study used the descriptive analytical approach through conducting interviews and distributing questionnaires. The study found that there was an intermediate level of satisfactions for the international humanitarian interventions in response by the beneficiaries and an intermediate level of satisfactions for the partners institutions in management of international humanitarian interventions. The study recommended to activate the national center of crises and disaster to act quickly during crises, and to build a national system for coordination between all humanitarian interventions at the national and local level.

Realities and challenges of relief operation in shelters during 2014 aggression on Gaza from the beneficiaries and service providers' perspective (Case study-Beit Hanoun Area) - (Alburai, 2018)

The study aimed at studying the reality of the relief work during the aggression of 2014 and determine the obstacles of the coordination and the relief work. The study used the descriptive analytical methodology depending on data collected from questionnaires and interviews. The study found that of the main factors that impacted the relief work during 2014 aggression were the lack of a clear strategy for the relief agencies to provide the services and communicate, lack of needs' registry system in addition to the lack of communication with the IDPs to determine their needs and having services' satisfaction feedbacks. The study recommended forming a joint central operation room between the governmental, local and international organizations as well as developing a software program to monitor the work of the sectors and determine their needs and weaknesses.

International and local NGO supply chain collaboration: An investigation of the Syrian refugee crises in Jordan - (Adem et al., 2017)

The study aimed at identifying the key drivers and challenges to supply chain collaboration in the humanitarian sector and to appraise the relationships between international non-governmental organizations (INGOs) and local non-governmental organizations (LN-GOs) during disaster relief. The study used the qualitative method and discussed literature from the commercial and humanitarian sectors. The study found that resources sharing between INGOs and LN-GOs would facilitate effective coordination of activities for refugee care and that the poor communication between INGO and LN-GO partners results in poor planning and logistic process failures. The study recommended further investigation into the approaches addressing the diverse cultural and decision-making perspectives of Local NGOs and INGOs.

Coordination with international organizations and its role in supporting the governmental health sector in Gaza Strip - (Al-Ghouti, 2015)

The study aimed at identifying the coordination with international organizations and its role in supporting the health sector in the Gaza Strip and to recognize the obstacles hindering the coordination process. The study used the descriptive analytical methodology depending on data collected from questionnaires and interviews. The study found that the political situation in the Gaza Strip and its impact on the international organizations response hinders the coordination between the international organizations and the public health sector. The study recommended enhancing the role of good coordination between international organizations and the public health sector and preparing and updating a guideline including the priorities of the various needs and activities of the public health sector.

The institutions of civil society and its impact on the oversight role of Community development in the United Arab Emirates – Public welfare associations – Case study - (Hosani, 2013)

The study aimed at identifying the role of the civil society organizations in the development of the community in the United Arab Emirates and in identifying the relationship between the civil society organizations and the state. The study used both the descriptive analytical method and the historical method. The study found that the complementary role between the civil society organizations and the state helped developing and serving the community in the United Arab Emirates. The study recommended the need to draft regulations for the actual partnership between the state, the civil society organizations and the private sector

and strengthening the proper strategic planning to the civil society organizations where their programs are sustainable.

The coordination of actors intervening in crisis following natural disasters: the issues arising in the emergency-development transition. The case of Haiti - (Fiscale, 2011),

The study aimed at identifying the managerial and coordination challenges among actors involved in the emergency-development transition phase following the Haiti earthquake and their implications in terms of effectiveness and appropriateness of the humanitarian intervention. The study used literature review and interviews in the field with the most relevant actors involved in the coordination. The study found that a common communication strategy still seems to be lacking among Information Managers of cluster lead-agencies, the international staff in charge of participating in coordination forums are poorly familiar with grassroots problems and the highly qualified national staff are lacking due to poor training to local staff. The study recommended each cluster to have a governmental counterpart, include the beneficiaries in the projects' phases, invest in resources to foster coordination mechanisms at municipal and departments level and hire more senior staff to perform coordination functions.

A Study of NGO Relations with Government and Communities in Afghanistan - (Jelinek, 2006)

The study aimed at looking at the relationship between provincial and central government actors, communities and NGOs, investigating NGOs' engagement with government structures, and what can they achieve in engaging with each other. The study used inductive qualitative research strategy, including observations, structured, semi-structured interviews, and group discussions. The study found that there is a favorable impression of NGOs by the government that is where NGOs had involved the government through sharing information about their plans, programs, and activities, inviting them to events, trainings, workshops, etc. and coordinating activities with them. The study recommended that NGOs to continue the development of a more coordinated approach with Government ministries and keep them up to date with their activities, design their programs in line with the government plan and priorities, and have MoU with the government including clear roles and responsibilities. Government should support NGOs as partners in humanitarian and development work and develop a strategic partnership with NGOs, acknowledging their skills and expertise and learning from them.

Theoretical framework

In May 2021, tension rose in East Jerusalem around access restrictions of Palestinians to holy sites during the month of Ramadan and the threat of forced eviction of Palestinian families by the Israeli authorities in Sheikh Jarrah. In response and in solidarity with Palestinians there, an outbreak of hostilities in Gaza has resulted. Between 10 and 21 May, the gravest fighting between Israeli forces and Palestinian armed groups in Gaza Strip since 2014 has intensified (OCHA, 2021). The humanitarian consequences of this escalation have been devastating, exacerbating the impact of around 14 years of Israeli blockade, internal Palestinian political divisions and recurrent escalations. According to the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), 261 Palestinians were killed, including 67 children and 41 women; of those fatalities, 130 were civilians. Over 2,200 Palestinians were injured, including 685 children and 480 women, some of whom may suffer a long-term disability requiring rehabilitation. At the height of the escalation, 113,000 internally displaced persons (IDPs) sought shelter and protection at UNRWA schools or with hosting families. According to the Shelter Cluster 8,250 people remain displaced, as their houses were destroyed or severely damaged (OCHA, 2021). International organizations, including the United Nations

and its specialized agencies, donor representative agencies, and international nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) have always played a key role in delivering assistance in the occupied Palestinian territories (oPt). Since the creation of the Palestinian Authority (PA) in 1994, these organizations' activities have been coordinated with the PA in accordance with its national development priorities (Qarmout and Beland, 2012). NGOs are considered as independent, impartial and neutral agencies that provide relief, rehabilitation, reconstruction and / or development assistance. The relationship between NGOs and governments have occasionally been tense, where a government is sometimes afraid of being replaced by NGOs and/or exposed for a lack of accountability and transparency with donor or public funds. Governments may also view NGOs as potential competitors for donor funding. NGOs work also at the grassroots level to provide aid, services, and information to those in need as well as a wider audience of policymakers, state organizations, and donor agencies (Jelinek, 2006). It should also be noted that the relationship between the non-governmental organizations and the government is not of one nature, such relationships differ from one case to another and have many forms and mechanisms. This is attributed to a number of variables that are related to the nature and directions of the political regime in the country in addition to the nature of activity of such non-governmental organizations and their relationships with the external and internal powers (Muamer, 2011). At all times, both non-governmental organizations and the government should be sharing the same goal which is to prioritize assistance to beneficiaries who are in need of support and interventions (Jenlik, 2006). Due to the humanitarian coordination and financial instruments, more lives are being saved, more quickly and efficiently (OCHA, 2012). Coordination is the systematic use of policy instruments to deliver humanitarian assistance in a cohesive and effective manner. Such instruments include strategic planning, gathering data and managing information, mobilizing resources and assuring accountability, orchestrating a functional division of labor in the field, negotiating and maintaining a serviceable framework with host political authorities and providing leadership (Minear et al., 1992). In Gaza Strip, and at times of emergencies, a high level of coordination is maintained between the actors working in emergencies to better respond to the affected population (Abu Dayya, 2019). This has been proven in the response to the escalation in 2014, where governmental bodies like the Ministry of Social Development (MoSD) has managed and led the relief work in Gaza Strip through cooperation and coordination with all the international organizations, local organizations, municipalities and other community bodies. All the challenges faced during the escalation made it crucial for MoSD to coordinate at all levels to facilitate its response to the affected people (MoSD, 2015). In May 2021 escalation, where, in addition to the devastating consequences, a caseload of IDPs has resulted. Over 70,000 have been displaced in UNRWA schools during the hostilities and most of them returned home after the cessation of hostilities. However, at the current time, over 9,000 people remain displaced due to the destruction and damage of their homes and are in need for humanitarian interventions including sheltering services (OCHA, 2021).

Study Tool

After reviewing the studies of Abu Dayya, 2019 and Alghoti, 2015 and the CBM Core Humanitarian Standards Self-Assessment report 2018, the researcher reached out to the following questions as the study tool that are in the below schedules of respondents' answers:

Ministry of Social Development (MoSD)

1. Nature of Coordination between organizations

1. Governmental Organizations- Intergovernmental coordination

Table (1): Nature of coordination between the governmental organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Does the ministry coordinate with other ministries?			The ministry coordinates with the Ministry of Interior, National Security and Ministry of local Governance based on the nature of the crisis
2.	Are the staff aware of the importance of coordination among themselves?			The ministry applies the coordination protocol within the ministry emergency plan
3.	Does the ministry have a special coordination committee to coordinate with other ministries?			The ministry is a member in the governmental committee that includes all the ministries engaging during emergencies
4.	Has the ministry developed a plan to trigger complementary relationships with other ministries?			There is a governmental plan that includes the role of each ministry
5.	Do the Staff have the experience to coordinate with other ministries?			The experiences vary based on the training the staff received and their work experience in different emergency committees
6.	Does the ministry exchange human resources and expertise with other ministries?			Ongoing meetings in general
7.	Does the ministry exchange information and data with other ministries about their programs and services?			A unified database exists between all the governmental organizations
8.	Are there joint action plans between the ministry and other ministries?			A unified governmental plan that includes the roles of each ministry
9.	The ministry benefits from the expertise of other ministries to develop its services?			Mostly with Ministry of Public Work and Housing

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the governmental organizations in Gaza coordinate with each other, are aware of the importance of coordination and have the required experiences. However, the levels of coordination planning differ due to the risks associated with the different crises in Gaza Strip. There are disparities in the coordination between governmental organizations, and for this reason, there are attempts to have the best coordination model despite challenges. In order to achieve that, some mechanisms are being deployed such as a governmental committee that includes all the ministries engaging during emergencies, a joint governmental plan that includes the role and responsibilities of each ministry and a unified database between all the governmental organizations where information and data about their programs and services is shared.

2. Coordination between governmental and non-governmental organizations (NGOs, INGOs, UN and local organizations)

Table (2): Nature of coordination between the governmental and non-governmental organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Is there a MoU or clear understanding or policy between the organization and the related ministry?			There is an international structure during emergencies led by OCHA (Emergency Coordination Center)
2.	Are there periodical meetings between the organization and the related ministry?			Types of meetings differ per the risks' nature

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
3.	Does the coordination between the organization and the government positively impact the efficiency of the organization work?			The work of the organization is linked with the increase in coordination efficiency
4.	Is the relationship between the organization and the government considered complementary?			Some gaps exist in terms of the quick response of the organizations to activate the status of emergency and respond
5.	Is there a clarity of roles and responsibilities each party have to do?			Roles differ according to the work, goals and internal system of the organization; MoSD role is supervision and senior coordination
6.	Are the governmental officials aware of the importance of coordination with the humanitarian organization and how to make use of it?			MoSD seeks enhancing and developing coordination to realize the humanitarian standards and ensure the humanitarian interventions are in line with the needs of affected population

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the level of coordination between the humanitarian non-governmental organizations and the governmental bodies is reflected in having clear roles and responsibility, periodic joint meetings and in being part of the international structure during emergencies that is led by OCHA (Emergency Coordination Center). Those results are in agreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which found that there is a favorable impression of NGOs by the government that is where NGOs had involved the government through sharing information about their plans, programs, and activities, inviting them to events, trainings, workshops, etc. and coordinating activities with them. The results are also in line with the recommendation of the same study that called the NGOs to continue the development of a more coordinated approach with Government ministries and keep them up to date with their activities, design their programs in line with the government plan and priorities and have MoU with the government including clear roles and responsibilities, where in this regards the government said that instead of having MoU there are coordination structure where roles are clarified. It was also found that the coordination between the humanitarian non-governmental organizations and the governmental bodies positively impacts the efficiency of the organization work and the relationship is considered complementary; however, some gaps exist in terms of the quick response of the humanitarian organizations to activate the status of emergency and respond. In the same context the study of (Hosani,2018) found that there is a complementary role between the civil society organizations and the government and that helped developing and serving the community in the United Arab Emirates.

2. Level of Coordination

Table (3): Level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Communication between the governmental and humanitarian organizations has an effective impact on the success of coordination?			Meetings are conducted during emergencies with the international organizations specifically OCHA and UNRWA

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
2.	The level of information exchange between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal?			There is a time difference in the quick response of the humanitarian non-governmental organizations. The time between the service delivery and the implementation notification to the ministry; by that time other responding organizations would have responded leading to duplication in services provided.
3.	There is a joint and effective cooperation between governmental and humanitarian organizations?			The efficiency of coordination between governmental and humanitarian non-governmental organizations is linked with the ability to have coordination policies in partnership with relevant stakeholders
4.	The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations decreases the time and efforts?			Coordination has increased during May escalation and COVID-19 response to a great extent
5.	The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal to some extent?			Achieving the aspired goal depends on the level of the government involvement of humanitarian organizations in developing coordination mechanisms
6.	Are the interventions conducted by humanitarian organizations identified in consultation with the related ministry (according to priorities)?			The ministry shares their ways forward with the non-governmental humanitarian organizations; some revert, ask for more information and discuss with the ministry while others (few in numbers) proceed in their mandate and work without consultations even if it doesn't relate to the emergency status; this causes some disruption to the ministry during emergencies
7.	The governmental organizations provide updated information on the needs of IDPs?			There is a matrix with the NGOs that includes all the information required and needs of people affected (specifically during May escalation)

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the communication between the governmental and non-governmental humanitarian organizations has an effective impact on the success of coordination specifically during emergencies which is in line with the results of (Adem et al. 2017) that found that poor communication results in poor planning and logistic process failures.

According to the above table, it was also found the level of information exchange between the governmental and humanitarian non-governmental organizations achieves the aspired goal; however, there is a time difference in the response provided by the humanitarian organizations that may lead to duplication in services provided. The study of (Jelinek, 2006) also agreed that the NGOs sharing information with the government about their plans, programs and activities or through other mechanisms proved a favorable impression by the government. It was also found that the interventions conducted by humanitarian non-governmental organizations are not identified in consultation with the related ministry according to priorities and that the ministry shares information on their way forward, their needs and resources but not all the organizations reach out and consult with the ministry which led to disruption. This comes in disagreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which recommended the NGOs to design their programs in line and consultation with the government plan and priorities. Moreover, there is a joint and effective cooperation between the governmental and humanitarian organizations where the current level of coordination between them decreases the

time and efforts and achieves the aspired goal to some extent and this was witnessed during May escalation and COVID-19 responses. MoSD also mentioned that the updated information on the needs of IDPs are shared on a matrix that NGOs have access to, such a system was recommended by (Alburai, 2018) where the lack of needs' registry system impacted the relief work during 2014 aggression.

3. Coordination Tools:

Table (4): Coordination tools within the governmental organizations

	Coordination Tool	Humanitarian Organization	Governmental bodies	Comments
1.	Periodic meetings are conducted between concerned stakeholders			On a daily basis and whenever required
2.	Coordination committee exists to coordinate with other bodies			There is an emergency governmental committee that includes all the relevant stakeholders. The ministry is involved in the cluster system under the umbrella of OCHA. Periodic meetings are ongoing
3.	Involved in the coordination meetings			Coordination meetings happen at both governmental and non-governmental levels.
4.	Joint goals and objectives are discussed and agreed upon with other stakeholders.			Goals are shared to avoid duplication of efforts and to provide the humanitarian response at the suitable time and according to the quality criteria.
5.	Use of written communication to coordinate with other stakeholders			Written communication is used through emails in addition to virtual meetings.
6.	Plans and programs are shared with other stakeholders			Every organization knows its roles. This helps reaching all the targeted populations and avoiding duplication of efforts.
7.	Visits are exchanged to learn from others' experiences and experiments			An assessment after each emergency/event involving the related focal points is conducted considering all the observations and notes and then a report is developed. No joint trainings to all the teams in terms of roles were conducted, however joint drills and simulations where each implemented their roles was conducted
8.	Joint workshops are organized with other stakeholders			Joint workshops are organized to benefit from each other's' experiences and to exchange points of views.
9.	Assessments information is shared with the relevant coordination groups in a timely manner and in a format that can be readily used by other humanitarian agencies			At the governmental level, a main database exists that can be accessed by all ministries. For the INGOs and local NGOs, MoSD data can be accessed through a special account. There is a matrix for the Emergency Coordination Center

	Coordination Tool	Humanitarian Organization	Governmental bodies	Comments
10.	The organization policies and strategies include a clear commitment to coordination and collaboration with others, including national and local authorities without compromising humanitarian principles			There is a manual specifying the roles at the governmental level. The structure with the humanitarian organizations is also clear
11.	How is information about the organization's competences, resources, and areas and sectors of work shared with others responding to the crisis?			
	Through reports published at the governmental level during response which include the resources, where they were spent, the needs and any other observations and through other coordination tools such as the matrix, meetings ...etc.			
12.	How do programme plans include measures to regularly share information and coordinate activities with other national and international stakeholders?			
	Through the governmental manual and the cluster system			

From the above table, it becomes clear that MoSD uses a variety of coordination tools both at the governmental and non-governmental levels. Some traditional tools like meetings, workshops, discussions are used, which is in agreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which found the positive impact behind involving both governmental and non-governmental organizations together through information sharing, trainings and workshops. The MoSD also deploys other tools including a governmental manual, emergency committees, a governmental database, a matrix that is shared with the humanitarian organizations and reporting in emergencies which comes also in line with the recommendations of the same study that called to keep developing coordination approaches with the government.

4. Humanitarian Interventions

Table (5): Humanitarian interventions within the governmental organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Do you have prior planning to respond to emergencies?			There is a reference frame, standards and pre-formed committees
2.	Do you collect indicators that an emergency may occur?			Through ongoing follow up (winter storms, at the political side)
3.	Do you seek support from external experts when planning for emergencies?			An external expert, through OCHA, has previously provided a training on how to manage emergency shelters
4.	Do you have preventive measures at your organization before the emergency occurs?			An emergency structure exists, and a team is defined. MoSD usually guides national and international organizations to be prepared
5.	Do you have scenarios for effective response?			Two drills/simulations were conducted virtually in 2020 on how to respond to an emergency status
6.	Are gaps in response identified and addressed?			The issue is in the availability of resources to respond during emergencies. Another issue is the delayed declaration of the emergency status in the organizations. The response from the resources of MoSD is usually faster than the response of the organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
7.	The organization participates in relevant coordination bodies and collaborates with others in order to minimize demands on communities and maximize the coverage and service provision of the wider humanitarian effort?			The international organizations are informed of the affected areas, the expectations and the needs so that only the affected people are responded to.
8.	How does programming coordinate with other actors (NGOs, government agencies, etc.) and take their programmes into account when designing, planning and implementing programmes? When the emergency plan is formed, all stakeholders and their roles, resources and capacities are included.			
9.	How are activities that directly involve people and communities harmonized with those of other actors who work with the same populations? MoSD always try to decrease the duplication but can't prevent it as there are no one organization whether governmental or non-governmental that can cover all the needs rather it depends on existing capacities. During emergencies, May 2021, the partner international organizations depended on the data from MoSD and were granted access to MoSD database that includes information about IDPs. In case there are extra assistances, needy vulnerable families are assisted even if not affected by the emergency itself (escalation)			

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that when it comes to interventions, MoSD is considering some measures including planning, collecting indicators, taking preventive measures and conducting simulations/drills. MoSD coordinates with all relevant stakeholders and coordination bodies in emergency and focuses its efforts to minimize the duplication that may result during response. Those results are in agreement with the study of (Hosani, 2013) that called for the partnership between all relevant stakeholders and focused on the need to strengthen strategic planning of NGOs.

Humanitarian Non-Governmental Organizations:

* OXFAM

1. Nature of Coordination between organizations

1. Inter-humanitarian organizations coordination

Table (6): Nature of coordination between the humanitarian organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Does the organization coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?			Coordination level varies based on the work nature of each organization.
2.	Are the staff aware of the importance of coordination among themselves?			Staff are aware of the importance of coordination to a great extent; the coordination is always maintained at different levels during their work.
3.	Does the organization have a special coordination committee to coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?			There is a focal point for each sector
4.	Has the organization developed a plan to trigger complementary relationships with other humanitarian organizations?			Coordination is maintained through other mechanisms
5.	Do the Staff have the experience to coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?			Staff have coordination experience due to the organization's nature of work
6.	Does the organization exchange human resources and expertise with other humanitarian organizations?			Human resources and expertise are shared in order to share and benefit from other experiences

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
7.	Does the organization exchange information and data with other organizations about their programs and services?			Information is exchanged in alignment with the humanitarian principles to serve the affected population
8.	Are there joint action plans between the organization and other NGOs?			There are partnerships with other organizations
9.	Does the organization benefit from the expertise of other NGOs to develop its services?			Good practices are shared to benefit from the different experiences

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the humanitarian organizations in Gaza coordinate with each other, are aware of the importance of coordination and have the required experiences. To facilitate the coordination, Oxfam has sector focal points and is part of the cluster system where they coordinate and share information with other organizations, has joint action plans and exchange human resources and expertise with other humanitarian organizations through partnerships. However, they don't have a specific plan to trigger the complementary relationships with other humanitarian organizations rather such relationships are maintained through other ways. Those results come in agreement with the findings of (Adem et al., 2017) study that sharing resources between International NGOs and Local NGOs would facilitate effective coordination of activities, including for refugee care and that the poor communication between them results in poor planning and logistic process failures.

2. Coordination between Governmental and non-governmental organizations (NGOs, INGOs, UN and local organizations)

Table (7): Nature of coordination between the governmental and non-governmental organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Is there a MoU or clear understanding or policy between the organization and the related ministry?			More specifically with MoPWA
2.	Are there periodical meetings between the organization and the related ministry?			Periodical meetings are done on a regular basis and whenever required.
3.	Does the coordination between the organization and the government positively impact the efficiency of the organization work?			Mainly it does, but sometimes the coordination is not at the required level, thus not positively impacting the efficiency of the organization work.
4.	Is the relationship between the organization and the government considered complementary?			The relationship is considered complementary, as this achieves the objectives of humanitarian interventions.
5.	Is there a clarity of roles and responsibilities each party have to do?			The roles are clear through the Cluster system and through being involved through the governmental coordination structures, tools and mechanisms like the matrix.
6.	Are the governmental officials aware of the importance of coordination with the humanitarian organization and how to make use of it?			Awareness on the coordination importance exists to some extent.

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the level of coordination between the humanitarian organization (OXFAM) and the governmental bodies is reflected in having clear roles and responsibility, periodic joint meetings, and high efficiency of work. Those results are in agreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which found that through

involving the government in NGOs plans and activities and coordinating with them, a favorable impression was received and thus encouraging coordination with the government. The results are also in line with the recommendation of the same study that called the NGOs to continue the development of a more coordinated approach with Government ministries, keep them up to date with their activities, and have MoU with the government including clear roles and responsibilities.

It was also found that the coordination between the humanitarian organization (OXFAM) and the governmental bodies positively impacts the efficiency of the organization work and the relationship is considered complementary. In the same context, the study of (Hosani,2018) found that there is a complementary role between the civil society organizations and the government and that helped developing and serving the community in the United Arab Emirates.

2. Level of Coordination

Table (8): Level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Communication between the governmental and humanitarian organizations has an effective impact on the success of coordination?			Communication is considered an important level of coordination
2.	The level of information exchange between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal?			The ultimate goal of exchanging information is help supporting the affected population
3.	There is a joint and effective cooperation between governmental and humanitarian organizations?			The cooperation was proved through ongoing programs and partnerships
4.	The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations decreases the time and efforts?			To some extent, sometimes coordination requires extra times and efforts
5.	The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal to some extent?			Coordination saves lives and decreases the impact of vulnerabilities on people
6.	Are the interventions conducted by humanitarian organizations identified in consultation with the related ministry (according to priorities)?			Consultations are always required to clearly address the interventions' target areas
7.	The governmental organizations provide updated information on the needs of IDPs?			Following May 2021 escalation, updated lists of IDPs were provided to OXFAM for intervention

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the communication between the governmental and humanitarian organization (OXFAM) has an effective impact on the success of coordination which is in line with the results of (Adem et al. 2017) which found that poor communication, which is a level of coordination, results in poor planning and logistic process failures. According to the above table, it was also found the level of information exchange between the governmental and humanitarian organization (OXFAM) achieves the aspired goal and that there is a joint and effective cooperation between the two parties. This is in line with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) that found that the NGOs sharing information with the government about their plans, programs and activities or through other mechanisms proved a favorable impression by the government. It was also found that the interventions conducted by Oxfam are identified in consultation with the related ministry according to priorities. This comes in agreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which recommended the NGOs to design their programs in line and consultation with the government's plan and priorities.

When it comes to sharing updated information of IDPs, OXFAM confirmed receiving the needed information from the government side.

3. Coordination Tools:

Table (9): coordination tools within the humanitarian organizations

	Coordination Tool	Humanitarian Organization	Governmental bodies	Comments
1.	Periodic meetings are conducted between concerned stakeholders			Meetings are regularly conducted with humanitarian and governmental organizations
2.	Coordination committee exists to coordinate with other bodies			There are focal points supporting the coordination
3.	Involved in the coordination meetings			OXFAM is part of the cluster system and other coordination systems under OCHA
4.	Joint goals and objectives are discussed and agreed upon with other stakeholders			Oxfam goals and programs are discussed through partnerships and the consortium approach involving a number of key actors to achieve specific goals
5.	Use of written communication to coordinate with other stakeholders			Written communication is the main way of communication with others in addition to in-person and virtual meetings
6.	Plans and programs are shared with other stakeholders			Oxfam plans are shared to minimize the duplication and benefit the maximum number of population
7.	Visits are exchanged to learn from others' experiences and experiments			To some extent.
8.	Joint workshops are organized with other stakeholders			Workshops involving a variety of stakeholders are organized to share experiences and exchange points of views
9.	Assessments information is shared with the relevant coordination groups in a timely manner and in a format that can be readily used by other humanitarian agencies			It is much important to share information about need assessments with others, so no assessment is done twice or needs of specific categories are missed
10.	The organization policies and strategies include a clear commitment to coordination and collaboration with others, including national and local authorities without compromising humanitarian principles			Commitment to coordination is the basis of OXFAM's work where humanitarian principles are always respected
11.	How is information about the organization's competences, resources, and areas and sectors of work shared with others responding to the crisis? Through the official cluster system, encouraging collaboration, encouraging consortium approach and working in partnership with local NGOs			
12.	How do programme plans include measures to regularly share information and coordinate activities with other national and international stakeholders? Through the cluster system			
12.	How do programme plans include measures to regularly share information and coordinate activities with other national and international stakeholders? Through the governmental manual and the cluster system			

From the above table, it becomes clear that OXFAM uses a variety of coordination tools with different stakeholders. Some traditional tools like meetings, workshops, discussions are used with governmental and humanitarian organizations, which is in agreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which found the positive impact behind involving both governmental and non-governmental organizations together through information sharing, trainings and workshops. OXFAM also has focal points to coordinate with other bodies and the staff are involved in the coordination meetings where Assessments' information is shared in a timely manner and in a format that can be readily used by other humanitarian agencies

OXFAM shares its resources, competencies and information through the official cluster system, encouraging collaboration, encouraging consortium approach and working in partnership with local NGOs

4. Humanitarian Interventions

Table (10): Humanitarian interventions within the governmental organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Do you have prior planning to respond to emergencies?			Contingency plan exists
2.	Do you collect indicators that an emergency may occur?			Depending on sector specific indicators
3.	Do you seek support of external experts when planning for emergencies?			Through global advisors
4.	Do you have preventive measures at your organization before the emergency occurs?			Some measures are in place to minimize the impact of emergencies
5.	Do you have scenarios for effective response?			OXFAM developed scenarios to enhance response
6.	Are gaps in response identified and addressed?			Example: financial resources
7.	The organization participates in relevant coordination bodies and collaborates with others in order to minimize demands on communities and maximize the coverage and service provision of the wider humanitarian effort?			OXFAM has ongoing partnerships and coordinate with all stakeholders
8.	How does programming coordinate with other actors (NGOs, government agencies, etc.) and take their programmes into account when designing, planning and implementing programmes? Through meetings, information sharing and the cluster system.			
9.	How are activities that directly involve people and communities harmonized with those of other actors who work with the same populations? Through coordination mechanisms (meetings, 4ws system, information sharing)			

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that OXFAM is considering some measures when it comes to its interventions for emergencies including planning through having a contingency plan, collecting sector-specific indicators, taking preventive measures and having scenarios for effective response. OXFAM coordinates with other stakeholders and share information through meetings, the cluster system and other coordination mechanisms.

Those results are in agreement with the study of (Hosani, 2013) which called for the partnership between all relevant stakeholders and focused on the need to strengthen strategic planning of NGOs.

• **AISHA Association for Women and Child Protection:**

1. Nature of Coordination between organizations

1. Inter humanitarian organizations coordination

Table (11): Nature of coordination between the humanitarian organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Does the organization coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?			Yes, through the cluster system.
2.	Are the staff aware of the importance of coordination among themselves?			The staff clearly understand that coordination is important to achieve the organization's humanitarian goals
3.	Does the organization have a special coordination committee to coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?			Aisha is a member in the protection cluster and coordinate and share information with cluster coordinator and members and other humanitarian organization
4.	Has the organization developed a plan to trigger complementary relationships with other humanitarian organizations?			The relationships are organized clearly through the cluster system
5.	Do the Staff have the experience to coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?			It depends on the organization's nature of work
6.	Does the organization exchange human resources and expertise with other humanitarian organizations?			Aisha partners with other organizations to complement the human resources and to share experience with each other
7.	Does the organization exchange information and data with other organizations about their programs and services?			Yes, following the humanitarian principles
8.	Are there joint action plans between the organization and other NGOs?			Through partnerships with other organizations
9.	Does the organization benefit from the expertise of other NGOs to develop its services?			Through sharing good practices and lessons learnt

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the humanitarian organizations in Gaza coordinate with each other, are aware of the importance of coordination and have the required experiences. To facilitate the coordination, Aisha is part of the protection cluster where they coordinate and share information with the cluster members, have joint action plans and exchange human resources and expertise with other humanitarian organizations through partnerships. However, they don't have a specific plan to trigger the complementary relationships with other humanitarian organizations rather such relationships are maintained through other ways. Those results come in agreement with the findings of (Adem et al., 2017) which found that sharing resources between International NGOs and Local NGOs would facilitate effective coordination of activities, including for refugee care and that the poor communication between them results in poor planning and logistic process failures.

2. Coordination between Governmental and non-governmental organizations (NGOs, INGOs, UN and local organizations)

Table (12): Nature of coordination between the governmental and non-governmental organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Is there a MoU or clear understanding or policy between the organization and the related ministry?			AISHA is licensed by the Ministry of Health for the mental health clinic and services
2.	Are there periodical meetings between the organization and the related ministry?			Periodic meetings are conducted all the time to improve aspired results
3.	Does the coordination between the organization and the government positively impact the efficiency of the organization work?			The government is a main source of information that helps building interventions
4.	Is the relationship between the organization and the government considered complementary?			None of the parties can provide the whole assistance required, this can only be done through coordination and complementary relationships
5.	Is there a clarity of roles and responsibilities each party have to do?			There are specific units and staff dedicated to serve their roles based on the nature of the projects and their competencies
6.	Are the governmental officials aware of the importance of coordination with the humanitarian organization and how to make use of it?			This is proved through the ongoing follow-up and engagement

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the level of coordination between the humanitarian organization (Aisha) and the governmental bodies is reflected in having clear roles and responsibility, periodic joint meetings, high efficiency of work. Those results are in agreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which found that through involving the government in NGOs plans and activities and coordinating with them, a favorable impression was received and thus encouraging coordination with the government. The results are also in line with the recommendation of the same study that called the NGOs to continue the development of a more coordinated approach with Government ministries, keep them up to date with their activities, and have MoU with the government including clear roles and responsibilities. It was also found that the coordination between the humanitarian organization (Aisha) and the governmental bodies positively impacts the efficiency of the organization work and the relationship is considered complementary. In the same context the study of (Hosani,2018) found that there is a complementary role between the civil society organizations and the government and that helped developing and serving the community in the United Arab Emirates.

2. Level of Coordination

Table (13): Level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Communication between the governmental and humanitarian organizations has an effective impact on the success of coordination?			Communication helps sharing ideas and information and facilitating response
2.	The level of information exchange between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal?			Coordination is the success element to achieve the organization's goals
3.	There is a joint and effective cooperation between governmental and humanitarian organizations?			On a regular basis

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
4.	The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations decreases the time and efforts?			Coordination accelerates the interventions of the organizations
5.	The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal to some extent?			Through the government support, the humanitarian interventions are conducted effectively in a timely manner
6.	Are the interventions conducted by humanitarian organizations identified in consultation with the related ministry (according to priorities)?			Whenever there are new priorities, consultations with the government are done
7.	The governmental organizations provide updated information on the needs of IDPs?			Reflecting on May 2021 escalation, Aisha didn't receive timely updated information about IDPs and thus delaying the required interventions through Aisha

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that the communication between the governmental and humanitarian organization (Aisha) has an effective impact on the success of coordination which is in line with the results of (Adem et al. 2017) that found that poor communication, which is a level of coordination, results in poor planning and logistic process failures. According to the above table, it was also found the level of information exchange between the governmental and humanitarian organization (Aisha) achieves the aspired goal and that there is a joint and effective cooperation between the two parties. This is in line with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) that found that the NGOs sharing information with the government about their plans, programs and activities or through other mechanisms proved a favorable impression by the government. It was also found that the interventions conducted by Aisha are identified in consultation with the related ministry according to priorities. This comes in agreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which recommended the NGOs to design their programs in line and consultation with the government's plan and priorities. When it comes to sharing updated information of IDPs, Aisha said they didn't receive the needed information from the government side whereas MoSD said it has an accessible matrix including the information on IDPs that NGOs can use.

3. Coordination Tools:

Table (14): coordination tools within the humanitarian organizations

	Coordination Tool	Humanitarian Organization	Governmental bodies	Comments
1.	Periodic meetings are conducted between concerned stakeholders			Such meetings allow the exchange of ideas to achieve the harmonization required
2.	Coordination committee exists to coordinate with other bodies			Based on the nature of coordination required
3.	Involved in the coordination meetings			Involved in the cluster system
4.	Joint goals and objectives are discussed and agreed upon with other stakeholders			Stakeholders are all involved in the discussion of interventions' objectives
5.	Use of written communication to coordinate with other stakeholders			The written communication is the main tool of communication, other tools such as meetings are also used

	Coordination Tool	Humanitarian Organization	Governmental bodies	Comments
6.	Plans and programs are shared with other stakeholders			Plans and programs are shared at the governmental, non-governmental and the community level
7.	Visits are exchanged to learn from others' experiences and experiments			In order to enhance interventions
8.	Joint workshops are organized with other stakeholders			To exchange experiences
9.	Assessments information is shared with the relevant coordination groups in a timely manner and in a format that can be readily used by other humanitarian agencies			With both governmental and humanitarian organizations
10.	The organization policies and strategies include a clear commitment to coordination and collaboration with others, including national and local authorities without compromising humanitarian principles			Commitment to coordination is not stated in policies rather through different coordination structures and mechanisms
	1. How is information about the organization's competences, resources, and areas and sectors of work shared with others responding to the crisis? AISHA has strong ties and high coordination with various non-governmental organizations and strong links with governmental organizations. AISHA is also an active member in the Gaza Strip Child Protection Network (CPN) that is led by the Ministry of Social Affairs, and an active member in the Protection cluster; the Child Protection /MHPSS group led by UNICEF, and the legal task force. Therefore, the information sharing occurs in high coordination with partners and external consultants and expertise.			
12.	How do programme plans include measures to regularly share information and coordinate activities with other national and international stakeholders? AISHA, in designing their projects, coordinates with Sub working groups to share information and coordinate activities with other national and international stakeholders.			

From the above table, it becomes clear that Aisha uses a variety of coordination tools with different stakeholders. Some traditional tools like meetings, workshops, discussions are used with governmental and humanitarian organizations, which is in agreement with the study of (Jelinek, 2006) which found the positive impact behind involving both governmental and non-governmental organizations together through information sharing, trainings and workshops. Aisha coordinates with other bodies through the cluster system where it is an important member and the staff are involved in the coordination meetings where assessments' information is shared with both governmental and humanitarian organizations in a timely manner and in a format that can be readily used by other agencies. Aisha shares its resources, competencies and information through the cluster system and high coordination with partners and the direct engagement with the government. Activities are coordinated with national and international stakeholders.

4. Humanitarian Interventions

Table (15): Humanitarian interventions within the governmental organizations

	Question	Yes	No	Comments
1.	Do you have prior planning to respond to emergencies?			AISHA has contingency and emergency plan
2.	Do you collect indicators that an emergency may occur?			Through the experience in crises and data collection
3.	Do you seek support of external experts when planning for emergencies?			Through ideas exchange and trainings
4.	Do you have preventive measures at your organization before the emergency occurs?			Trainings to staff, emergency team and others
5.	Do you have scenarios for effective response?			This helps during the immediate management of the crisis
6.	Are gaps in response identified and addressed?			Depending on the capacities available
7.	The organization participates in relevant coordination bodies and collaborates with others in order to minimize demands on communities and maximize the coverage and service provision of the wider humanitarian effort?			The main goal of Aisha is to protect the affected population and provide assistance as much as possible
8.	How does programming coordinate with other actors (NGOs, government agencies, etc.) and take their programmes into account when designing, planning and implementing programmes? When AISHA design, plan and implement their programs, they usually involve all stakeholders in need assessment and focus groups to design the programs based on their needs			
9.	How are activities that directly involve people and communities harmonized with those of other actors who work with the same populations? When AISHA design projects, they adopt theory of change which include three levels of intervention (individuals, community, and duty bearers).			

From the above table, it becomes clear to the researcher that Aisha is considering some measures when it comes to its interventions for emergencies including planning through having a contingency and emergency plan, collecting indicators, taking preventive measures and having scenarios for effective response. Aisha involves all the relevant stakeholders (including individuals, community, and duty bearers) through the project/program phases, and this is done through meetings, focus group discussions, information sharing and the cluster system. This comes in agreement with the study of (Fiscala, 2011) which recommended to include the beneficiaries in the projects' phases, invest in resources to foster coordination mechanisms and the study of (Hosani, 2013) who called for the partnership between all relevant stakeholders.

Similarities and differences of the responses:

Area	Similarities	differences
Nature of Coordination	<p>Inter-organizations coordination Both the humanitarian and governmental organizations coordinate with each other and their staff are aware of the importance of coordination and have the experience required Both the humanitarian and governmental organizations have their own coordination mechanisms that ranges from having focal points and being part in committees. Each the humanitarian and governmental organizations have a kind of joint action plans and unified plan between each other. Each the humanitarian and governmental organizations exchange information about their programs and services with each other.</p>	<p>Inter-organizations coordination The humanitarian organizations don't have a specific plan to trigger the complementary relationships with other humanitarian organizations while the governmental organizations have a joint governmental plan that includes the role and responsibilities of each ministry. The humanitarian organizations exchange human resources and expertise with other humanitarian organizations through partnerships and benefit from others' expertise to develop their services while the governmental organizations do not exchange human resources and expertise with others, however they regularly conduct meetings and they benefit from others' expertise to develop their services.</p>
	<p>Coordination between Governmental and non-governmental organizations There are clear roles and responsibilities between the humanitarian and governmental organizations where they are engaged in joint meetings including during emergencies in the coordination and emergency structure. The coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations positively impacts the efficiency of their work. Both also considered the relationship between them complementary; however, the governmental organization said there are some gaps in terms of the quick response of the humanitarian organizations to activate the status of emergency and respond. Both the humanitarian and governmental officials are aware of the importance of coordination between each other and how to make use of it.</p>	
Level of Coordination	<p>The communication between the humanitarian and governmental organizations effectively impacted the success of coordination; this was clear in the response to emergencies. The level of information exchange between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal; however, according to the governmental organization, there is a time difference in the response provided by the humanitarian organizations that may lead to duplication in services provided. There is a joint and effective cooperation between the governmental and humanitarian organizations The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations decreases the time and efforts and achieves the aspired goal to some extent and this was witnessed during May escalation and COVID-19 response.</p>	<p>The interviewed governmental organization said that the interventions conducted by humanitarian organizations are not identified in consultation with the related ministry according to priorities and clarified that the ministry share information on their way forward, their needs and resources but not all the organizations reach out and consult with the ministry which led to disruption. However, the interviewed humanitarian organizations said their interventions are identified in consultation with the related ministry. The interviewed governmental organization said that updated information on the needs of IDPs are shared on a matrix that NGOs have access to. However, one of the interviewed organizations confirmed that while the other said that they didn't receive update information on IDPS.</p>

Tools of Coordination	<p>Periodic meetings and joint workshops are conducted and the plans and programs are shared with other stakeholders. The organizations' joint goals and objectives are also discussed and agreed upon with other stakeholders. Both organizations are involved in coordination meetings and have either focal points or are part of different coordination mechanisms like the cluster system or the governmental emergency committee at the government level.</p> <p>To learn from others' experiences and experiments, the interviewed humanitarian organizations exchange visits however the governmental organization said they conduct an assessment after each emergency and conduct simulations/drills to enhance their capacities.</p> <p>Assessments' information is shared with the relevant coordination groups in a timely manner and in a format that can be readily used by other humanitarian agencies; a matrix was also made available by the governmental organization to NGOs partners.</p> <p>There is a clear commitment by the humanitarian and governmental organizations to commitment within strategies/policies or other ways; including the governmental manual specifying the roles and responsibilities and the humanitarian coordination structure. However, one of the humanitarian organizations said that commitment is not stated within their policies and strategies.</p> <p>The governmental and humanitarian organizations have different ways sharing their competencies and areas of work; the governmental organization focused on the reporting during emergencies to reflect resources, needs and gaps while the humanitarian organizations in general are encouraging collaboration and partnerships and are engaged in the cluster system in which the governmental organizations are also involved.</p> <p>Both organizations share information and coordinate with different stakeholders through the cluster system or using the governmental manual at the government level.</p>	
Humanitarian Interventions	<p>The governmental and humanitarian organizations plan to respond to emergencies in different ways; the humanitarian organizations have emergency and contingency plans while the governmental have reference frame, standards and pre-formed committees</p> <p>Both organizations collect indicators that an emergency may occur through continuous follow up and having sector specific indicators.</p> <p>Both organizations seek the support of external experts when planning to emergencies.</p> <p>Preventive measures are taken before an emergency occurs; guidance is also provided by the government to the national and international organizations</p> <p>Scenarios and simulations/drills are conducted for effective response and gaps are identified and addressed.</p> <p>Both organizations participate in coordination bodies and collaborate to ensure assistance has reached the communities without duplication resulted</p> <p>All stakeholders are included when planning for emergencies and information is shared with them</p> <p>To harmonize the responses provided, coordination mechanisms are put in place including meetings, information sharing and database (at the governmental level).</p>	

Findings

1. Coordination is an essential component of the humanitarian and governmental organizations' work that positively impact the efficiency of their interventions
2. For effective response, both humanitarian and governmental organizations coordinate and partner with each other and with relevant stakeholders including governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. The relationship between the humanitarian and governmental organizations is complementary and is maintained within their work of and not necessarily stated in specific plans.
4. The roles and responsibilities of the governmental and humanitarian organizations are clear and explained through coordination mechanisms.
5. The governmental organizations developed platforms to share information with all stakeholders in order to facilitate the provision of response.
6. The governmental organizations identified some gaps in the response to May 2021 escalation that are represented in the delayed response time and the declaration of emergency status by the humanitarian organizations; there was a delay in the opening of emergency shelters and in the provision of services.
7. Governmental organizations share the needed information on their capacities and resources with other stakeholder to encourage collaboration and ensure effective coordination and response
8. The cluster system under the umbrella of OCHA is an effective coordination platform involving both humanitarian and governmental organizations.
9. Humanitarian organizations develop their own contingency and emergency plans to respond to emergencies.
10. The governmental organizations involve all the related stakeholders and their resources in their emergency plans
11. The coordination between the humanitarian and governmental organizations achieved its goals to some extent.
12. The updated information on the IDPS of May 2021 escalation was made available by the MoSD however it didn't reach all stakeholders.
13. Different tools of coordination are being used by both governmental and humanitarian organizations including periodic meetings, joint workshops, information exchange, plans and programs sharing, visits exchange, drills and simulations and the involvement in governmental and non-governmental (international) coordination structures.
14. The level of coordination in response to May 2021 escalation was proved good however more improvements are required for effective interventions and response.

Recommendations

1. The humanitarian organizations to respond to the emergency in a quicker way as any delay in the response, even if the scale of the emergency is small, would cause negative impact.
2. The time difference in service provision to be tackled; as by the time a list of affected people is shared with an organization and them starting to respond, a gap occurs

where a duplication in services or deprivation of timely assistance to people can happen.

3. The activation of the IDPs working group under the Inter-Cluster Coordination Group to improve the response to IDPs.
4. To widely disseminate and encourage the access of the humanitarian organizations to the database of MoSD where all information required exists.
5. Humanitarian organizations to accelerate response to make use of their resources available.
6. Improve the coordination and collaboration between the governmental and humanitarian organizations to the greatest extent possible for further effective response.

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Annexes:

Study Tool

1. Nature of Coordination between organizations

1. Governmental Organizations

Inter-governmental coordination

Does the ministry coordinate with other ministries?

What are the coordination tools used?

Are the staff aware of the importance of coordination among themselves?

Does the ministry have a special coordination committee to coordinate with other ministries?

Has the ministry developed a plan to trigger complementary relationships with other ministries?

Do the Staff have the experience to coordinate with other ministries?

Does the ministry exchange human resources and expertise with other ministries?

Does the ministry exchange information and data with other ministries about their programs and services?

Are there joint action plans between the ministry and other ministries?

The ministry benefits from the expertise of other ministries to develop its services?

2. Inter humanitarian organizations coordination

Does the organization coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?

What are the coordination tools used?

Are the staff aware of the importance of coordination among themselves?

Does the organization have a special coordination committee to coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?

Has the organization developed a plan to trigger complementary relationships with other humanitarian organizations?

Do the Staff have the experience to coordinate with other humanitarian organizations?

Does the organization exchange human resources and expertise with other humanitarian organizations?

Does the organization exchange information and data with other ministries about their programs and services?

Are there joint action plans between the organization and other NGOs?
The organization benefit from the expertise of NGOs to develop its services?
Coordination between Governmental and non-governmental organizations (NGOs, INGOs, UN and local organizations)
Is there a MoU between the organization and the related ministry?
Are there periodical meetings between the organization and the related ministry?
Does the coordination between the organization and the government positively impact the efficiency of the organization work?
The relationship between the organization and the government is considered complementary?
Is there a clarity of roles and responsibilities each party have to do?
Are the governmental officials aware of the importance of coordination with the humanitarian organization and how to make use of it?

2. Level of Coordination

Communication between the governmental and humanitarian organizations has an effective impact on the success of coordination?
The level of information exchange between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal?
There is a joint and effective cooperation between the governmental and humanitarian organizations?
The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations decreases the time and efforts?
The current level of coordination between the governmental and humanitarian organizations achieves the aspired goal to some extent?
Are the interventions conducted by humanitarian organizations identified in consultation with the related ministry (according to priorities)?
The governmental organizations provide updated information on the needs of IDPs?

3. Coordination Tools:

Coordination is conducted through periodic meetings between concerned stakeholders?
Do you have a coordination committee to coordinate with other bodies?
The teams are involved in the coordination meetings?
Do you have joint goals and objectives agreed upon with other stakeholders?
Do you depend on written communication to coordinate with other stakeholders?
Do you share your plans and programs with other stakeholders?
Do you exchange visits to learn from others experiences and experiments?
Do you organize joint workshops with other stakeholders?
How is information about the organization's competences, resources, and areas and sectors of work shared with others responding to the crisis?
How do programme plans include measures to regularly share information and coordinate activities with other national and international stakeholders?
The organization policies and strategies include a clear commitment to coordination and collaboration with others, including national and local authorities without compromising humanitarian principles?
Do you share assessment information with the relevant coordination groups in a timely manner and in a format that can be readily used by other humanitarian agencies?

4. Humanitarian Interventions:

Do you have prior planning to respond to emergencies?

Do you collect indicators that an emergency may occur?

Do you seek support of external experts when planning for emergencies?

Do you have preventive measures at your organization before the emergency occurs?

Do you have scenarios for effective response?

How does programming coordinate with other actors (NGOs, government agencies, etc.) and take their programmes into account when designing, planning and implementing programmes?

Are gaps in response identified and addressed?

The organization participates in relevant coordination bodies and collaborates with others in order to minimize demands on communities and maximize the coverage and service provision of the wider humanitarian effort.

How are activities that directly involve people and communities harmonized with those of other actors who work with the same populations?